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ADVANTAGES OF USING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING MATHEMATICS

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Abstract. This article analyzes the advantages of using digital technologies in teaching mathematics. In the modern educational process, interactive programs, electronic platforms and multimedia tools are an important factor in increasing the level of students' mastery of mathematical knowledge. Also, digital technologies expand the opportunity to visually explain complex examples and problems, which develops students' logical thinking and independent work skills. The article highlights the role of distance learning, online testing systems and virtual laboratories in improving the quality and efficiency of education. In addition, it is emphasized that the use of digital tools strengthens cooperation between teachers and students, serves to organize lessons in an interesting and innovative way.

Keywords: mathematics, digital technologies, interactive education, electronic platform, multimedia tools, distance learning, innovative approach, virtual laboratory, online test, educational efficiency.

Today, the issue of modernizing the education system and improving its quality is one of the priority tasks in the world. In particular, the rapid development of information and communication technologies has a great impact on the educational process, as well as on all areas. Therefore, the effective use of digital technologies in teaching subjects has become an urgent issue. Mathematics, as it is based on accuracy, logical thinking and complex calculations, is one of the subjects that most requires the use of digital tools. Modern programs, electronic platforms, virtual laboratories and multimedia tools are playing an important role in the effective organization of mathematics lessons. The use of digital technologies in teaching mathematics makes the process of learning more interesting and interactive for students. In traditional teaching methods, students often have difficulty understanding complex formulas and theoretical concepts. Digital technologies make it possible to visually display mathematical processes. For example, the content of formulas can be explained in a simple and understandable way through graphics, animations and interactive programs. This increases students' interest in the subject and develops their independent thinking skills.

Digital technologies also create wide opportunities for teaching mathematics in the form of distance learning. Through online platforms, students have the opportunity to gain knowledge anywhere and at any time. Electronic tests, virtual classes and automated assessment systems facilitate the rapid identification and control of students' knowledge. As a result, the effectiveness of the educational process increases and cooperation between teachers and students is strengthened[1].

Currently, various innovative projects are being implemented in many countries to digitize mathematics education. This contributes to the acquisition of modern knowledge and skills by the younger generation. In this regard, studying the advantages of using digital technologies in teaching mathematics and analyzing their impact on the quality and efficiency of education is of great scientific and practical importance.

Nowadays, digital technologies are deeply penetrating all aspects of human life. The education system is not left out of this process. In particular, the use of modern technologies in teaching mathematics is an important factor in increasing the efficiency of the learning process. Since mathematics is a science based on precise calculations, formulas and logical conclusions, the

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use of interactive tools in explaining it gives great results. With the help of digital technologies, students master complex topics faster and easier, and teachers have the opportunity to organize lessons in an interesting and effective way.

One of the main digital tools used in teaching mathematics is multimedia technologies. Multimedia tools are presented by combining text, sound, video, animation and graphics. For example, when teaching geometry topics, showing the movement of shapes through animation helps students understand the subject more deeply. If it is difficult to imagine three-dimensional shapes using a regular blackboard and chalk, they can be rotated, enlarged or divided into pieces using multimedia tools. This develops students' spatial imagination.

For example, when explaining the formula for finding the area of a circle, the teacher uses the following formula:

$$S = \pi r^2$$

In the traditional method, the formula is explained only by writing. However, with the help of digital programs, it is possible to show how the surface of a circle changes when its radius changes through an animated graph. This method creates a practical understanding of the formula in students.

Also, graphic programs are of great importance in teaching the topic of functions in algebra. Many students have difficulty imagining the graphical appearance of a function. With the help of special programs, the graph of a function can be generated in real time. For example, let's take the following linear function:

$$y = 2x + 3$$

On digital platforms, a student can change the coefficients and observe how the graph moves. This helps to understand mathematical relationships in a practical way. In particular, programs such as GeoGebra and Desmos are effective tools for interactively organizing mathematics lessons.

Another important advantage of digital technologies is the expansion of opportunities for independent learning. Currently, there are many electronic textbooks, video lessons, and test platforms on mathematics on the Internet. The student can also do additional exercises outside of class and consolidate his knowledge. For example, during the test on online platforms, incorrectly answered questions are automatically analyzed and the student's mistakes are shown. This develops students' skills in working on themselves.

Virtual laboratories also play an important role in teaching mathematics. The use of virtual tools is especially effective in analyzing statistical data and conducting experiments on probability theory. For example, performing an experiment on the topic of probability by flipping a coin a hundred times in ordinary conditions takes a lot of time. The virtual laboratory performs this experiment in a few seconds and displays the results in the form of a diagram. This increases students' interest in the subject and makes it possible to connect theoretical knowledge with practice[2].

In addition, digital technologies are also of great importance in the development of distance learning. During the pandemic, many educational institutions switched to an online learning system and various platforms were used for distance learning in mathematics. Videoconferencing, electronic assignments, and online assessment systems have ensured that the learning process continues uninterrupted. For example, a teacher can explain methods for solving equations via an online platform and show examples step by step on the screen.

When explaining the topic of quadratic equations, the following formula can be used:

$$x = \frac{-b \pm \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a}$$

Digital programs allow you to interactively observe how roots are formed when the values in the formula change. This method makes it easier for students to remember the formula.

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Digital technologies also create many conveniences for teachers. For example, using electronic journals and automatic assessment systems, you can quickly analyze student results. The teacher determines which topics are difficult for students and organizes additional classes. At the same time, the ability to store lesson materials in electronic form and reuse them saves time.

The use of artificial intelligence elements in teaching mathematics is also one of the current trends today. Some modern programs analyze the student's level of knowledge and give him individual tasks. For example, students who are weakly mastering are presented with simple examples, and students with high results are presented with complex problems. This provides an individual approach[3].

Digital technologies also expand the opportunity to connect mathematics with real-life examples. For example, when explaining the topic of interest, examples of bank loans or trade discounts can be used. Students begin to understand the practical importance of mathematics by calculating real-life problems. For example, the process of calculating interest on a bank deposit can be explained using the following formula:

With the help of this formula, students also learn the concepts of investment and savings.

In general, the use of digital technologies in teaching mathematics serves to improve the quality and efficiency of education. With the help of modern technologies, lessons are organized in an interactive, understandable and interesting way. Students' logical thinking, independent work skills and creative approach are developed. Therefore, the wider use of digital technologies in mathematics education will be important in the future.

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